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CORRELATION BETWEEN BREAST SIZE AND DOSIMETRIC PARAMETERS FOR RADIATION THERAPY OF BREAST CANCER

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Introduction: Radiation therapy (RT) is considered a standard approach in adjuvant treatment of early-stage breast cancer after breast conserving surgery. The RT of left-sided breast cancer is challenging because of the risk of late side effects to the heart and lungs, therefore importance of minimizing dose to these organs at risk (OAR) is well recognized. The primary aim of this study was to investigate impact of breast size on dose coverage of planning target volume (PTV) and doses to organs at risk.

Materials and methods: A retrospective analysis of 30 left-sided breast cancer patients who underwent breast-conserving surgery and adjuvant whole breast tangential, forward intensity-modulated radiation therapy (F-IMRT) using field-in-field technique was done. The total prescribed dose was 50 Gy in 25 fractions. For all patients dose constraints were fulfilled in accordance with ICRU Report.

Patients were divided into three groups according to breast size by measuring the clinical target volume (CTV) (small size: $V_{CTV} < 975 \text{ cm}^3$; medium: $975.0 \text{ cm}^3 < V_{CTV} < 1600.0 \text{ cm}^3$; large: $V_{CTV} > 1600 \text{ cm}^3$). To determine the influence of breast size on dose distribution, parameters related to absorbed dose coverage of PTV ($D_{100\%}$) and OAR sparing ($V_{20\text{Gy}}$ and $V_{5\text{Gy}}$ for heart and $V_{20\text{Gy}}$ for left lung) were analysed.

An additional investigation of relationship between breast size and field number was also undertaken.

Statistical analysis was performed by using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The significance level was set at p -value < 0.05 .

Results: The analyses of the PTV absorbed dose coverage and dose-volume constraints related to lung was not found to be significantly different across the three group according to breast size. Considering absorbed dose to heart statistically significant difference was found for V_{20Gy} , the lowest dose was for small volume breast size ($p < 0,00658$). Difference between total numbers of field was also found to be statistically significant, the highest number was found for large breast size ($p < 0,03339$).

Conclusion: In this study the influence of patient breast size on dosimetric parameters was investigated. There was found very little difference between patients of different breast size. Statistically significant difference in total number of fields at F-IMRT technique is an indicator of plan complexity. More fields are needed to achieve acceptable dose coverage of target volume at large breast size.

Keywords: breast cancer, whole breast radiation therapy, forward IMRT, breast size, dosimetric evaluation

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